

Review Article

A place where “You can be who you’ve always wanted to be...” Examining the ethics of intelligent virtual environments

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of interactive virtual reality (VR) spaces like VRChat has been made possible due to continuing increases in computer processing power, advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), and advances in 3D modelling and spatial and edge computing. Perhaps because these spaces rely on new ways of integrating different forms of advanced computing, such as AI and VR, little is yet known about their potential ethical implications. In this contribution, we provide an overview of key themes frequently discussed in the context of these so-called *Intelligent Virtual Environments* (IVEs). We highlight different ethical questions and the ways in which they are typically taken up in the literature. We first map how common concerns tend to revolve around technological feasibility and psychological impacts. We then ask how shifting the focus towards more philosophical perspectives might reorient discussions surrounding IVEs, opening up important avenues for future research. Our contribution in this review is to highlight how as active mediators of experience these technologies require critical reflection and should not be evaluated solely in terms of their functionality.

Welcome to the world of Intelligent Virtual Environments (IVEs)

On July 11th 2022, the media network HBO released a trailer for the documentary, *We Met in Virtual Reality*. Filmed and directed by Joe Hunting, the documentary initially premiered at the Sundance Film Festival to largely favourable reviews. With the tagline “You can be who you’ve always wanted to be”, it is the first feature-length documentary film shot entirely in virtual reality (VR). Hunting used a virtual camera tool, VRCLens, to shoot the entire film inside one of the most popular social VR platforms, VRChat. With a large community of dedicated users, VRChat allows users to interact using custom avatars, create their own content (such as rooms and experiences), and is free and open to use with or without a VR headset. The *We Met...* trailer documents the experiences of an American Sign Language teacher, a fitness dance instructor, as well as numerous individuals who used VRChat to create or maintain relationships throughout the COVID-19 lockdowns.

Despite attracting a modest 40,000 views in its first week on YouTube, the trailer’s comments section quickly became a hotbed of discussion regarding the desirability and purpose of the film. For example, users who actively engage in VRChat, commented that the trailer was both exciting and scary, with regards to the potential repercussions of

introducing VRChat to a more mainstream audience. A recurring concern amongst multiple users was that the media’s response to the film would only highlight the negative aspects of these spaces, emphasizing their lack of oversight and governance or tendency towards toxicity, where discrimination, bullying, and sexual harassment quickly seem to become the norm.

Other users acknowledged the importance of seriously engaging with the darker side of spending time in VR environments. Some seem to suggest that the trailer appears to reflect a somewhat idealized picture, resulting in many comments expressing users’ hopes that a balanced representation of the wide range of VRChat experiences—both the positive *and* the negative—would be represented in the full feature-length film. Commenters acknowledge that while greater oversight might be desirable in some cases, (e.g. in the case of protecting children), it was exactly the lack of oversight that attracted some of VR’s early adopters. It is made clear that for users who identify as belonging to marginalized groups, for example, VRChat provides a valuable and unique space, one where they can *really be themselves*.

The rapid development of spaces like VRChat has been made possible due to continuing increases in computer processing power, advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technologies such as natural language

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processing (NLP), and advances in 3D modelling and spatial and edge computing (Luck & Aylett, 2000). As suggested by Luck and Aylett, “This combination of intelligent techniques and tools, embodied in autonomous creatures and agents, together with effective means for their graphical representation and interaction of various kinds, has given rise to a new area at their meeting point”, which they call “*intelligent virtual environments*” (IVEs) (2000; see also Osório et al., 2005). IVEs integrate and embed AI techniques into the virtual environment, by incorporating AI algorithms into the system architecture itself, enabling the addition of problem-solving components as well as enhancing interactivity (see also Laukkanen et al. 2004). In the Metaverse, defined as “an expansive virtual space where users can interact with 3D digital objects and 3D virtual avatars of each other in a complex manner that mimics the real world” (XRToday, 2021), AI facilitates accurate avatar creation, supports embodied interaction, and generates content from the environment and characters, to other graphical objects and textures. Though multiple terms are used—often synonymously—to refer to these types of spaces, e.g. the metaverse, virtual worlds, and the similarly sounding *immersive* virtual environments (also IVE), to name but a few, we have chosen the term *intelligent* virtual environment, as it is not only a broad umbrella, but also because it emphasizes and draws attention to the convergence of AI and VR technologies. When it comes to real-world applications of IVEs, Dooley (2017) provides a number of examples, such as business training, security, vehicle maintenance, and retail; describing how virtual showrooms “can provide enhanced product selection while a learning algorithm customizes both products and the buying experience itself” (see also Meepung and Kannikar 2022). The term is also in common usage in and amongst the human computer interaction (HCI) community (see e.g. Anastassakis and Panayiotopoulos 2015, Köse et al. 2021, Latoschik and Fröhlich 2007, Mateus and Branch 2015, Piki et al. 2022, Rincon et al. 2017b, Rincon et al. 2014, Rincon et al. 2017a).

The recent publication of David Chalmer’s *Reality+* (Chalmers, 2022) has brought the discussion of some traditional philosophical problems in epistemology, philosophy of mind, and the philosophy of consciousness into dialogue with VR, and VR experiences. These questions extend discussions about VR from ethics into the domain of phenomenological method and ontology (a study of *what is qua what appears and how it appears*) (see also Coeckelbergh 2024). While many of these questions entail hypothetical scenarios, involving much more advanced and speculative forms of IVEs than are currently available, the questions raised are nonetheless relevant to the ethical consideration of existing IVEs. Ethical questioning and discussions about the ethics of IVEs to date, often pertain to the modality of appearance of objects and other subjects within IVEs, e.g. what is the ethical salience of objects or behaviour from other persons not experienced as fully “real”. While the relevance of phenomenological descriptions of first-person experiences in VR and IVEs is recognized in recent literature (Geniusas, 2022; Haj-Bolouri, 2023; Kelly et al., 2023), the debate about the nature and appropriateness of phenomenological analysis more broadly in empirical research is also highly relevant to the ethics of IVEs.

Though phenomenological analysis in empirical research is often understood to be a matter of increasingly fine grained descriptions of first person experiences and meaning-making activities, there is a lively discussion within the literature about whether this is an overly narrow understanding (see, for example, Smith 2018, van Menen 2017, Zahavi 2019a). The debate centres on whether phenomenological method is limited to first-person descriptions of experience (van Menen, 2017b) or instead aims at examining the conditions of possibility for how the world, its objects or specific regions, for example an IVE and the digital objects therein, appear as real or unreal, and what those distinctions mean (Zahavi, 2019 refers to Husserl 1970 to illustrate this). This latter understanding would also include questions about the conditions of possibility for the experience of varying types of experience of phenomena, for example, valuing and social norms. In the latter case, phenomenology is more closely connected to metaphysical questions. As

Zahvai (2019) writes: “We pay attention to how and as what worldly objects are given to us. By doing so, by analysing how and as what any object presents itself to us, we also discover the intentional acts and experiential structures in relation to which any appearing object must necessarily be understood.” The point is that phenomenological descriptions of first person experience in IVEs lead into more metaphysically loaded questions of how objects appear in IVEs and with what significance. This has ethical relevance and pertains to technical questions about how perceptual or phenomenal experiences within IVEs can be modulated by the technical infrastructure and architecture, as well as by governance structures. Moreover, with the development and potential deployment of more pervasive IVEs, ethical questions also lead us to questions about political ontology (“claims or assumptions that a particular approach to social [or, by extension, political] enquiry makes about the nature of social [or political] reality—claims about what exists, what it looks like, what units make it up and how these units interact with one another”) (Blaikie, 1993, see also Coeckelbergh 2024).

In a recent review of *Reality+*, Tim Crane provides an overview of the issues raised in Chalmer’s philosophical treatment of VR: “Does it matter whether the “people” you interact with in a VR machine are real? Can things have real value in VR? Does the source of value come from experience or from our actual relations and interactions with people?” (Crane, 2022). These questions, directly addressing the what and how of appearance within VR, or IVEs – how are “mattering” and “real value” constituted in experience within VR, or IVEs – are directly related to the ones above about the nature of phenomenological analysis in empirical research.

Much of the discussion around Chalmer’s analysis centres on the reformulation of the classic Cartesian “evil genie” problem. The simulation problem (qua update of the evil genie thought experiment) is slightly different from the hypothetical question raised by VR: given a hypothetical IVE wherein we are not able to tell the difference between the IVE and physical reality (PR), (1) how would we know whether we were experiencing the IVE or PR? And (2), how should we treat, epistemically, ethically, and politically the experiences, particularly the experiences of value that we have in an IVE? This discussion has stimulated a growing debate on the ethical, social and philosophical questions related to the increased availability and prevalence of IVEs in many areas of social interaction (see Metzinger 2018, Ramirez and LaBarge, 2018) and is linked to the phenomenological discussion outlined above through questions such as how does value manifest in phenomenal experience, and what elements of experience modulate its appearance.

The more general justification for taking a phenomenological approach to IVE ethics is that questions about values, norms, and ethical behaviour within IVEs cannot be treated in an abstract manner as distinct from questions about modes of appearance within IVEs. And the latter are independent from neither technical features of IVEs nor the interrelated governance structures.

The perceived importance of sociological, anthropological and philosophical perspectives in relation to digital, virtual environments and the metaverse can also be seen in growing calls for a “human-centric metaverse” (Yang et al., 2023) or the creation of “Metavethics” (Grinbaum & Adomaitis, 2022; Zallio & Clarkson, 2023) (building on earlier calls for a meta ethics of the metaverse, see Spence 2008). As a new field of study and domain of expertise, metavethics would approach “the scientific and the broader, technology-oriented communities with new questions and inspiring opportunities for the creation of digital, virtual environments that are framed within the context of acknowledging positive ethical implications for human beings” (Zallio & Clarkson, 2023, p. 683). As Zallio and Clarkson suggest, the creation of a metavethics would support designers and developers, “affording them new opportunities and ideas in order to preserve physical and psychological safety as well as the inclusion and privacy of every individual accessing and using the metaverse” (p. 688). These developments point to an array of issues that are currently coming to the fore in response to the emergence of IVEs.

In this contribution, we provide an overview of several key themes, including (but not limited to) physical and psychological safety, inclusion and privacy. We highlight different ethical questions and the ways in which they are typically taken up in the literature. We begin by proposing that in order to fully consider the range of ethical issues that are pertinent within the context of IVEs, we need to shift away from a narrow focus on feasibility towards a broader perspective that encompasses different levels of desirability. Next, we briefly describe how this review was conducted before mapping the emerging issues that we found to be most prevalent in the literature. We have categorised these issues according to the following themes: privacy preservation and data collection; affect, manipulation & behaviour change; accessibility, inclusion, and safety; public space and digital assets; and etiquette and governance. In each section, we first map how common concerns tend to revolve around technological feasibility and psychological impacts. We then ask how shifting the focus towards more philosophical perspectives might reorient the discussions surrounding IVEs, opening up important avenues for future research. Essentially, our contribution with this review is to highlight how as active mediators of experience these technologies require critical reflection and should not be evaluated solely in terms of their functionality (Versteeg, 2013).

Feasibility vs. desirability

In the last few years, the increased accessibility and availability of head mounted displays (HMDs) has accelerated interest in VR. In 2021, for example, almost 10 million VR devices shipped worldwide leading forecasters to predict a compound annual growth rate of about 15% until 2030 (Grand View Research, 2021). As a result, IVEs, such as VRChat, are being developed by a variety of stakeholders for a range of purposes. Perhaps the biggest focus within IVEs so far has been on the development of so-called “virtual humans”. For example, in the late 1990s, Lewis Johnson and his colleagues began developing an infrastructure for virtual pedagogical agents. According to Luck and Aylett (2000), their work sought “to create animated, persona-rich agents” that could use “eye contact and body language... in order to interact effectively with students” (p. 22). For example, the Soar Training Expert for Virtual Environments (STEVE) could monitor and control the virtual environment, showing students how to perform particular tasks, answer student questions, monitor performance, and give advice when the students ran into difficulties. Since the development of STEVE, the term virtual human has become an overarching category applied to virtual entities operating both within and beyond virtual worlds, including chatbots, conversational agents, and virtual mentors (e.g. Franklin and Graesser, 1996, Nwana 1996, Thalmann 1996, Reader and Savin-Baden 2020, Reilly and Bates 1992, Sycara et al., 1996; for a full review see Burden and Savin-Baden, 2019).

Essentially, from the showroom to the classroom, there has been considerable discussion regarding what is *technologically feasible* within IVEs. However, there has been far less attention given to what is *ethically desirable*. That is, to the possible ethical implications that may emerge when these different groups of technologies (e.g. AI and VR) converge. Concerning VR, ethical concerns originally arose in relation to practical considerations, e.g., simulation sickness, information overload, intensification of experience, and difficulties with re-entry into the real world (Behr et al., 2005). More recently, additional ethical concerns have revolved around topics like mental health issues, misrepresentation, immoral behaviour, implications for real-world behaviour, vulnerable populations, identity hacking, manipulation, exploitation, and desensitisation (see e.g. Brey 1999, Chirokoff 2017, Kenwright 2019, Pan et al. 2018, Slater et al. 2020, Spiegel 2018). So far, solutions to these problems have largely been based on technical interventions, making adaptations to the technology, the content, or the experimental design (Behr et al., 2005). For example, with regards to IVEs, considerable attention has been dedicated towards increasing the user’s experience with regards to embodiment, immersion, and presence, as it is generally

assumed that improving these features will improve the overall functionality of IVEs, specifically with regards to achieving their intended effects or aims.

Technically feasible and feasibly functional: Embodiment, immersion, & presence

According to Kilteni et al. (2012), visual perspective, vestibular signals, and tactile input all play a role in the self-localization of a user inside a virtual body. They refer to a “sense of embodiment” proposing a working definition, which includes a “sense of self-location, a sense of agency, and a sense of body ownership (p. 373) in relation the virtual body inhabiting the IVE. Concerning agency they argue that the “synchronicity of visuomotor correlations” is key. While in terms of body ownership, they suggest that “bottom-up” sensory information and “top-down” cognitive processes combine to produce the sense that the virtual body belongs to the user. Within VR, this sense of embodiment is considered vital when it comes to a variety of (interrelated) goals, such as promoting social values, stimulating empathy, or realising long-term behaviour change (Versteeg, 2013), all of these being closely related to embodiment, habit and affordance (Taylor, 2002).

In addition to stimulating a sense of embodiment, VR systems also try to create a sense of immersion, which is defined in terms of the technological qualities of IVEs; or the capacities of the technological medium to generate experiences that shut out physical reality (Slater & Wilbur, 1997). Levels of immersion can differ significantly from one environment to another, depending on the technological capabilities of each system. Characteristics used to gauge the extent of immersion typically include things like display resolution, audio quality, frame rate, tracking, and field of view (See Cummings and Bailenson 2016, Johnson and Stewart 1999, Oh et al. 2018, Skalski and Whitbred 2010, Welch et al., 1996). As Cummins and Bailenson (2016) suggest, given that systems of higher immersive quality appear to elicit greater psychological presence, it follows that “a designer seeking to maximize user presence should construct the most advanced, technologically immersive systems possible” (p. 275). According to Slater and Wilbur (1997), a system is more likely to be immersive if it is vivid (in terms of multi-sensory modalities); extensive (in terms of congruence between the physical and virtual body); and if it contains strong plots and narratives (in terms of the credibility of the scenario, also referred to as the “plausibility illusion”). Media are considered more immersive when they provide “an inclusive, extensive, surrounding and vivid illusion of reality to the senses of a human participant” (Slater & Wilbur, 1997, p. 604). Though it is typically assumed that higher levels of immersion elicit higher levels of presence, Cummings and Bailenson’s (2016) meta-analysis of research in this area suggests that technological immersion has only a medium-sized effect on presence, while some system features (e.g. user-tracking and field of view) have a more significant impact than Others (e.g. visual and auditory content).

Whereas immersion refers to the technological qualities of IVEs and is therefore considered an objective measure, presence refers to the psychological response of the user and is defined in terms of the “place illusion”, or the extent to which the user experiences the feeling of “being there” (Slater, 2009). An increased sense of presence is typically assumed to magnify the effect of the environment, whether it is oriented towards communication, education, or entertainment (See Cummings and Bailenson 2016, Nunez and Blake 2001, Price and Anderson 2007, Slater and Wilbur 1997, Tamborini and Bowman 2010, Tamborini & Skalski 2006). Within VR, presence has been defined according to three distinct subcategories (Lee, 2004; Oh et al., 2018). *Telepresence* refers to the extent to which the user feels present in the mediated virtual environment (Steuer et al., 1995); *self-presence* refers to the extent to which the user experiences the virtual self as the actual self (Ratan & Hasler, 2009; Aymerich-Franch, 2012); and *social presence* refers to the extent to which the user has the sense of being with Others (Biocca, 1997; Biocca & Harms, 2002; Biocca et al., 2003). Because studies have shown that

social presence can have a positive impact on communication outcomes, VR researchers have tried to identify the immersive, contextual, and psychological factors that impact perceptual social presence (Cummings & Wertz, 2018; Oh et al., 2018). Whereas maximising telepresence and self-presence is typically associated with making IVEs as technologically immersive as possible (e.g. the place illusion), social presence depends more on the context and credibility of engagement (e.g. the plausibility illusion) (Oh et al., 2018).

The question about the realness of VR is often posed in terms of a normative question related to whether or not an experience is somehow “authentic”. From a phenomenological perspective, a philosophical approach that examines the structures of subjective experience, this question of “authenticity” is something of a red herring. There is no apparent reason to argue that experiences in IVEs are not real or authentic experiences in the relevant sense of the term. What is relevant is the different modalities by which objects, and agents appear within IVEs and PR and how these modalities of appearance affect the manifestation of values, especially towards Other agents, human or not (O’Shiel, 2020). For example, the object of experience e.g. a table in an IVE may (will most certainly) appear as different to the object of experience of a table in PR in terms of how it is related both to the subject of experience, Other objects in the environment, and the perceptual environment itself. The experience of an object or anOther agent not being in PR does not make the experience or the object less authentic but different. O’Shiel (2020) makes the case for different forms of virtuality in PR and digital worlds. These different forms of virtuality mediate experiences of value in PR and IVEs. Empirical research enables us to identify the users of values in a specific context, as well as provide insights into how the use of IVEs could potentially mediate the values of users (see e.g. Smits et al. 2022b, Zuidhof et al. 2018, Smits et al. 2022a). How this mediation occurs, by what perceptual register, coupled with what technological mechanisms is a matter for further phenomenological investigation.

Wehrle (2020) for example, argues “distance or mediatedness within our embodiment” such as occurs or could occur within an IVE “can be understood as the precondition for explicit learning, reflection, as well as the development of culture and technology” (p. 518). The mediatedness does not degrade the authenticity of the embodied experience in a normative fashion. In a similar way, a hallucination may appear as different to Other objects in its perceptual environment, but it is still a real or authentic experience of a hallucination. Nonetheless, our valuation of these real but virtual entities could be affected by the modality of appearance, with subsequent practical concerns for safety, respect for Others, and harassment in IVEs as well as empathy levels, social inclusion, and effectiveness in various use contexts, e.g. education, therapy, and entertainment (Hamilton-Giachritsis et al., 2018; Kishore et al., 2021; Kleinsmith et al., Lok, 2015; Louie et al., 2018; Maggini, 2013; Roswell et al., 2020; Rueda & Lara, 2020; Schoeller et al., 2019; Schutte & Stilinović, 2017; Van Loon, Bailenson, Zaki, Bostick, & Willer, 2018).

There is a relation between the phenomenological approach outlined above and the “virtual realism” thesis offered by Chalmers (2022) in reference to Heim (2000) seminal work on virtual worlds. Chalmers’ thesis is that virtual objects and the worlds that contain them are real and not illusory. Objects experienced in IVE are experienced as real qua phenomenal experience, but also as having an underlying (real) ontology composed of bits and code, as opposed to whatever metaphysical picture of the world is correlated with our experience of PR. That picture of PR could be concordant with a “scientific” (up to date or not) worldview, or another ontology. To put this another way PR and VR can both be considered as parts of phenomenological (experienced) reality, having differing, we could say, “regional” ontologies. O’Shiel (2020) argues, in reference to Chalmers’ earlier work, that what is most salient are the modalities through which phenomena appear and how their appearance is mediated, in this case technologically: “Of course, phenomenologically and otherwise, there are virtual objects for the simple fact that we experience them. What is also quite obvious but not

noted by many, however, is the fact that they are given to consciousness through screens and other devices, and are thus already, by this very fact, experientially and even ontologically not the same as straightforward perceptions” (p. 3). This reinforces the point that the salient aspect of this discussion is not the “realness” of digital objects, but how their modes of appearance interact with modes of valuation and other ethically salient phenomena. Munn and Wiejers (2023) likewise argue that ethical concerns in IVEs do not stem from somehow reality impoverished experiences, but rather from governance and ownership structures (addressed below).

Whether and in how far qualities like embodiment, immersion, and presence are desirable beyond exploring what is technologically feasible, and what role they play in the appearance of value with IVEs has yet to be fully discussed (existing work in this vein includes Slater et al. (2020) on the ethics of realism and Madary and Metzinger (2016) on general ethical concerns in VR). Crucially, as Oh et al. (2018) point out, we should not treat embodiment, immersion, or presence as though they are an “absolute good” in and of themselves. For example, when it comes to instructional communication in computer-supported settings, more social presence may not always necessarily be beneficial when it comes to establishing and maintaining learner motivation (Allmendinger, 2010). As suggested earlier however, given the weight of attention these features receive within the VR world, they necessarily intersect with all of the themes we discuss below. Essentially, depending on whether IVEs are used for entertainment, learning, training, or therapy, it is critical to understand effects like embodiment, immersion, and presence from a wider range of perspectives than just the technological or psychological. As we discuss further below, applying a phenomenological lens helps draw attention to the ways in which these technologies mediate user experiences in different contexts.

Methodology

Insofar as this review brings together research on AI and VR both of which have been conceptualised differently and studied across various disciplines, reflecting a variety of different standpoints and perspectives, a semi-systematic review approach was adopted. Conducting a semi-systematic review entails mapping dominant themes which have emerged over time, drawing attention to how topics have developed across different research traditions (Snyder, 2019). Adopting this strategy enables the creation of meta-narratives which synthesise multiple perspectives, providing a broad overview of the main issues, helping to make sense of complex and often contested topics (Wong et al., 2013). Semi-systematic reviews rely on methods commonly used within qualitative research, particularly thematic and content analysis. These techniques provide a means for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns across a broad selection of texts (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Semi-systematic reviews are therefore particularly useful when it comes to detecting themes or common issues in relation to a particular research problem, in this case, identifying the relevant scholarly discussions in relation to the potential ethical implications of IVEs.

Whereas systematic literature reviews involve following a specific set of steps designed to answer a narrow research question, the semi-systematic review process is more exploratory and can therefore be tailored towards specific projects (Wong et al., 2013). Semi-systematic reviews involve making judgements and as such the approach cannot be prescribed through adherence to a checklist. However, Wong et al. (2013) do describe a number of guiding principles including: pragmatism, pluralism, historicity, contestation, and reflexivity which can be used to help ensure the transparency of the research process. By way of an example, the principle of pragmatism refers to the notion that the selection of what to include is not self-evident, but that the reviewer should be guided by what is likely to enable sense-making for the intended audience.

Following Wong et al.’s advice we first undertook an initial “territory mapping” exercise. This involved research using informal, unstructured

methods, desk research in libraries and internet databases, and consulting with experts and stakeholders (from project partners within the GuestXR consortium). This scoping step is an essential part of a semi-systematic review as it helps to provide an overview of the different research traditions and literatures relevant to the topic of interest. Having broadly mapped which areas of the AI and VR discourses were most relevant in the context of IVEs, we next compared and contrasted findings from these different traditions to build a rich picture of the topic from multiple angles.

An additional review was carried out using the literature database Scopus. Though Scopus has been shown to demonstrate biases in terms of topic coverage (e.g. a predominance of natural science and biomedical journals) and geographical distribution (e.g. journals published in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Western Europe), it still shows a better coverage of journals than other comparable databases (e.g. Web of Science), as well as a higher share of Social Science journals (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). The literature was identified by conducting an abstract/title search with the following terms: artificial intelligence OR "AI" and virtual reality OR "VR" OR mixed reality OR "MR" OR augmented reality OR "AR" OR extended reality OR "XR" AND ethical OR ethics. The search covered the years 2018–2023. The articles were screened independently by two researchers. We screened 167 unique articles and reviewed their abstracts. An additional search was conducted using Google Scholar and snowballing of the selected articles reference lists was also carried out in order to identify exemplar articles (hence the inclusion of several articles which pre-date 2018). As discussed earlier, based on our findings, we included articles which focused on ethical principles/issues, technological affordances, and critical concerns. Though we make no claim to be in any way exhaustive, we hope to shine a light on examples of key ethical issues emerging in the context of IVEs.

It is important to note that while some guidelines and codes of conduct for VR do already exist, they are all still largely speculative and anticipatory (see Bliznyuk, 2019; Kenwright, 2019; Madary & Metzinger, 2016; Ramirez et al., 2020; Spiegel, 2018). In addition, as has repeatedly been shown, for example, in the context of AI ethics, it is not at all clear that increased guidelines result in more ethical behaviour (Hagendorff, 2020). Similarly, while the European Commission has created a regulatory framework for AI based upon seven key requirements (human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, societal and environmental well-being, and accountability see e.g. *Artificial Intelligence Act (2023)*, it, like other guidelines, lacks sufficient legal or operational grounding (Smuha et al., 2021).

As IVEs look set to become more deeply embedded in the fabric of our everyday lives, it is important that developers, users and investors have access to robust ethical considerations that can potentially influence design and application processes. This includes ensuring that researchers and engineers involved in the design and development of IVEs are supported in operationalising abstract values like “fairness” and “well-being”.

In the introductory section we highlighted the importance of a phenomenological approach in IVE ethics. Concretely speaking, this means that research into the ethics of AI should prioritise descriptive accounts of subjective experiences within IVEs as well as taking into consideration the conditions of possibility for various forms of experience within IVEs, particularly experiences of valuing relating to objects of other persons in the IVE, as well as other ethically salient forms of experience. IVEs are of particular interest in this regard because the technical infrastructures and architectures of IVEs as well as governance structures offer possibilities for modulating the conditions of possibility of certain types of appearance, like those mentioned above by, for example, altering forms of embodiment within the IVE or even altering in real time the ways objects are experienced as ‘real’ or not (this would require an understanding of the different ways that objects appear as

‘real’ within IVEs, which requires a phenomenological investigation). This latter point brings the ethical discussion of IVEs into close proximity with the sub-field of post-phenomenology which investigates the technological mediation of embodied phenomenal experience; an IVE being a perceptual environment where experience is almost entirely technologically mediated in the most direct sense (Evans & Rzeszewski 2020; Ritter, 2021).¹ The importance of incorporating a phenomenological approach into IVE ethics runs as a kind of red thread through this article.

Within this contribution, we not only provide an overview of existing ethical concerns, but also draw attention to as yet overlooked ways of approaching the possible ethical implications of IVEs.

Emerging ethical issues in the context of IVEs

In our review of the literature, we identified a number of recurring ethical issues. In what follows, we have organised our discussion according to issues we identify as related to: privacy preservation and data collection; affect, manipulation & behaviour change; accessibility, inclusion, and safety; public space and digital assets; and etiquette and governance. In the following sections, we discuss how despite increasing consideration of ethical issues in the literature, the majority of concerns still tend to focus largely upon technological feasibility and psychological impacts. In each section, we then try to open up some of these issues to examine what they look like when they are subjected to alternative framings.

Privacy preservation & data collection

Perhaps unsurprisingly, embodiment, immersion, and presence are enhanced through the collection of personal data, including biomarkers such as eye movement, retina dilation, heart rate, and bodily gestures, as well as location, preferences, and actions. All of which raises issues relating to privacy preservation, data collection, and security (Acheampong et al., 2023; Benjamins et al., 2023; Tukur et al., 2023; Kizza, 2003; Abraham et al., 2022; Harborth, 2022; McGill et al., 2021; Zallio & Clarkson, 2022). Though these sorts of concerns are not new and have been raised about all forms of information technology (Ramirez et al., 2021). van den Hoven et al. (2014) suggest that the “interactive and especially immersive nature of VR and AR technologies, and the degree to which they more greatly affect user emotions, makes such concerns especially important” (p. 19). For example with regards to telepresence, there is a delicate balance between increasing and decreasing autonomy (Kizza, 2003). As Harborth (2022) suggests, what is problematic with regards to (in his case, augmented reality AR environments), is that they require “various different sensors gathering real-time, context-specific personal information about the users, causing more severe and new privacy threats compared to other technologies. These threats can have adverse consequences on information self-determination and the freedom of choice and, thus, need to be investigated as long as AR is still shapeable” (p. 288).

It is likely that IVEs will open up both the type and quantity of information that private companies can obtain about individuals in the future (Coyle & Thorson, 2001). Given that haptics technologies can be used both to provide input as well as receive computer generated touch output (Eid & Al Osman, 2015; Huisman, 2017), similar issues regarding privacy preservation and data collection also quickly emerge.

¹ There are on-going debates in the philosophy of technology relating to the validity of post-phenomenological methods; these are outside of the scope of this article. In addition, despite an obvious focus on how IVEs mediate experience—which is more in keeping with a post-phenomenological approach—we chose to refer to phenomenology broadly throughout so as to encourage sustained reflection on what phenomenological perspectives could add to discussions surrounding IVEs.

As Eid & Al Osman (2015), ask, for example, “would it be ethical for a computer to sense a user’s physical interactions and/or emotions? Would an ideal haptic-based affective interface compromise user privacy? Are users comfortable with having their touch/feelings sensed?” (p. 37).

These are all important questions since increasingly the functionality and use of IVEs will rely on capturing physiological data, tracking bodily movements (such as gestures, facial expressions, and eye gaze), as well as aggregating behavioural and social data from user activities within IVEs (Smith et al., 2023; Zallio & Clarkson, 2022). At the same time, the accuracy of tracking and behavioural data in identifying users in VR has been argued to make anonymity virtually impossible (Miller et al., 2020; Pfeuffer et al., 2019), which raises a number of important concerns, particularly regarding data privacy risks. For example, how is the data collected, processed and stored? Is the processing and storage secure? Are users aware of what data is being collected, when they gave consent did they have a sufficient understanding? (i.e. was it informed, is consent updated, can it be revoked by the user etc.). Does awareness about data collection change user experience within IVEs?

These sorts of privacy concerns are closely linked to concerns about surveillance. The themes of platform surveillance (Srnicek, 2017) and surveillance capitalism Zuboff (2023) are therefore particularly relevant within the context of IVEs (see e.g. Bibri and Allam 2022). Though at this stage the effects of VR as a mechanism for surveillance capitalism are still speculative, the potential is undoubtedly very real (Carter & Egliston, 2020; Mitrushchenkova, 2023). The idea is effectively, that digital platforms and companies increasingly use digital monitoring as a standard business practice. They accumulate, buy, and sell data, not only as a mechanism for profit, but also for power (Carter & Egliston, 2020). For example, Nieborg and Poell (2018) describe the “platformisation of cultural production”, where platforms like Google, Microsoft, and Meta promote use until the point of dependency. In order to sign up to online services or buy apps, for example, we are increasingly required to provide permission for our data to be synced between and across multiple platforms. Within IVEs, companies can then leverage this data in a variety of ways (see section on manipulation and behaviour change below).

In the end, we all have something to hide, or something that we do not want to share. Having the ability to maintain autonomy over the private dimension of our lives (and maybe that now includes things like our heart rate, eye movements or the blood flow in our cheeks) is generally understood to be an important part of what it means to live in a democratic society to ensure sufficient independence of thought and expression outside of unwanted external intervention (Boehme-Neßler, 2016). It is perhaps worth noting that the original theoretical elaborations of fascism envisaged a totalising governance apparatus that accompanied individuals everywhere they went – something akin to the constant data collection that can occur in IVEs. If we feel strongly about this we need to think about it when we build technical systems. Especially if those systems are going to be used widely and potentially even for the provision of some public goods.

Affect, manipulation & behaviour change

Because of its immersive, persuasive capabilities, VR has already been used in journalism, fundraising, art, social justice movements, and as a therapeutic tool geared towards the promotion of long-term behaviour change. Given that IVEs introduce new forms of data collection, additional questions about affect, user manipulation and behaviour change also begin to emerge (Harborth, 2022). The amount of granular biometric data that can be collected within IVEs opens up the possibility that changes could be implemented within virtual environments—in real-time—that users themselves would be unaware of e.g. how their eye movements or heart rate could potentially be used to trigger changes in the way that they respond. With the ability to combine data regarding people’s search terms, communication style, and social ties with

nonverbal data, such as gestures and facial expressions, IVE providers could also potentially identify individual users, and attempt to diagnose their mental state or presumed desires (Harborth, 2022; Miller et al., 2020; Pfeuffer et al., 2019; Won et al., 2014). Companies could then influence consumer choice through real-time feedback, or personalised advertisements in IVEs, even featuring the user themselves. Though right now this discussion may appear highly speculative, it is important to consider the possible implications of providing access to so much personal data, as well as the potential long-term effects of so-called “neuromarketing” or “big nudging” (the use of big data to nudge users) (Madary & Metzinger, 2016, p. 18).

Persuasive technologies have long been created with the intent to promote prosocial values or instil long-term behaviour change (Berdichevsky & Neuenschwander, 1999). In the context of IVEs however, several applications have been described as an especially good tool for nudging users “into being less racist, more sympathetic to homelessness, more caring about the environment, and to eating less meat” (Ramirez et al., 2020, p. 19). Because immersion and presence are both relevant to the social psychological phenomenon of construal levels—that is, the closer something is perceived to be to someone the more concrete it appears—IVEs are often positioned as a technology for “moral enhancement” that can improve the “empathy and moral imagination of the user” (Cotton, 2021, p. 107; see also Bertrand et al. 2018, Herrera et al., 2018, Ramirez, 2017, Fisher, 2017). However, according to Carter and Egliston (2020), the idea that VR mediates empathy and compassion for others has been the subject of much “uncritical industry boosterism” (p. 25). Much of this attention derives from the notion that VR represents “the ultimate empathy machine” (a term coined by VR filmmaker Chris Milk). The idea is that the immersive and embodiment capabilities of VR stimulate an empathic response in the user by connecting them with a broader ethical dilemma (Cotton, 2021).

But when it comes to inducing empathy in users, the degree to which this is possible and/or desirable is actually a complex question for a number of reasons (see e.g. Bender and Broderick 2021, Bollmer 2017, Carter and Egliston 2020, Hassan 2020, Hassapopoulou 2018, Heft-luthy 2019, Irom 2018, Loh 2017, Nash 2017, Sutherland 2015, Ventura et al. 2020). First, there is the broader philosophical question: what is empathy (Read, 2019)? Trying to articulate a clear definition is difficult, given that there are many different types of empathy ranging from emotional contagion to much more robust forms of perspective taking. There are also risks involved in promoting the idea that IVEs could be used to generate some understanding of other people’s experience (or the experiences of other groups, particularly marginalized groups). This is because using empathy to generate understanding might simply serve to reinforce existing biases and hierarchies. In addition, a well-established argument in moral and political philosophy is that certain forms of empathy can actually inhibit a more abstract, meta-understanding of certain issues—which is often necessary, for example, in the case of policy making (Prinz, 2011).

We do not intend to make an argument against empathy; but instead to offer a warning to avoid what can appear (at least within VR circles) as a sort of empathy idolatry, where empathy becomes a panacea for addressing complex societal issues. There may also be certain relevant cases where claims to “empathy” with other concrete types of person, in terms of feeling what it is like to be homeless or a refugee may be overblown, while nonetheless the VR experience is able to generate structurally similar experiences in users. For example the Stanford-developed VR experience, called “Becoming Homeless,” may not allow VR users to feel or understand in a comprehensive manner what it’s like to “become homeless, but nonetheless may provide relevant experiential analogues, such as the feeling of cognitive strain, surprise, need for constant vigilance, etc”. (Shashkevich, 2018). The focus on empathy within pro-social IVE applications also lends itself to phenomenological investigation. The experiential dimensions of empathy have been a key focus in recent phenomenological literature. Fernandez and Zahavi (2020), for example, suggest building an empathy concept from the

ground up that can be used to “identify the most fundamental form of empathy, [...] distinguish amongst the more derivative experiences and behaviors that are addressed by the same name and, ideally, determine the place of these phenomena in the field of nursing” (p. 2). Similar investigations, in different areas where the empathy concept is applied together with promissory claims about IVEs, could be helpful in understanding what empathic or empathy-like forms of experience different IVE systems could help to stimulate.

Given the degree of data that can be collected within IVEs, we need to find ways of thinking about what might constitute the ethical limits of nudging, including nudging toward empathy, within these environments. Especially prescient here, are the sorts of risks frequent use of these technologies could pose to children and adolescents (see [Kaimara et al. 2022](#)). This links back to our earlier question about privacy and consent, and perhaps the ways in which dynamic consent methods might be used within IVEs.

Accessibility, inclusion, & safety

Other areas that are important to address from as early as possible in IVE design processes, include accessibility, inclusion, and safety. These issues each capture a number of different concerns regarding the different affordances and constraints of IVEs. The sorts of questions that we need to keep in mind here concern how we try to make IVEs accessible, inclusive, and safe for as broad an array of users as possible. As [Zallio and Clarkson \(2022\)](#) argue, “in relation to the perception of accessibility what could be considered currently as a limitation in the physical world could potentially become an opportunity to create a new design language to shape inclusive digital immersive environments without barriers to accessibility” (p. 7). However, though VR is often posited to be an accessible medium (in large part due to its ‘natural’ or intuitive user interface), there is an emerging literature that focuses on how these technologies are less accessible than they may at first initially seem, where in fact, “the experiences of people in the physical world can be reflected as similar but amplified experiences in the digital world” ([Zallio & Clarkson, 2022](#)).

One of the key issues here has to do with disability and accessible design. For example, despite being framed as having a *natural* user interface—in the sense that it relies on movements and gestures of the body—this is not necessarily something that is intuitive or natural to *all* bodies. Specifically, the bodily interface for most VR devices presents accessibility issues for people with disabilities (e.g. the need to assume a standing position which can lead to problems regarding perspective or people with low vision) ([Gerling & Spiel, 2021](#); [Zhao et al., 2019](#); [Wong, Gillis & Peck, 2017](#)). Bodies are also central to touch experiences, but as mentioned earlier, while the focus within IVEs tends to be on the hands, as virtual touch expands its reach, questions arise as to what kinds of bodies are considered in its design and development ([Jewitt et al., 2020](#)). Ignoring these issues risks potentially ableist and exclusionary mechanisms becoming locked into the design of IVEs.

Much like ableist narratives, ideas surrounding gender and race can also become encoded into technological systems ([Benjamin, 2019](#); [Gebu, 2020](#)). As IVEs evolve, they run the risk of reproducing existing structural and systemic bias in a variety of ways. From automatic gender recognition systems to the names and voices of digital assistants like Siri and Alexa, technological systems can often serve to perpetuate harmful stereotypes ([Ajunwa et al., 2016](#); [Angwin et al., 2016](#); [Buolamwini & Gebu, 2018](#); [Chambers, 2018](#); [Hamidi et al., 2018](#); [Richardson et al., 2019](#)). In addition, within VR, there has already been a significant amount of discussion regarding gender-based discrimination, harassment and bias (see [Carter and Egliston 2020](#), [Outlaw and Duckles 2018](#), [Smith et al. 2023](#)). Experiences of sexual harassment are not uncommon, including multiple instances of “virtual groping” ([Belamire, 2016](#); [Wood et al., 2017](#)). When it comes to touch, as [Price et al. \(2021\)](#) make clear, it “is a cultural practice imbued with social norms concerning who can legitimately touch what and who, where, how and when” (p. 3). They

also point out that within VR touch has been “primarily associated with “things” rather than “Others”, framing the particular kinds of touch that are under consideration” (ibid). An important question here therefore concerns how we treat “virtual” harassment ([Danaher, 2018](#)). We might need to think about different kinds of virtually mediated harassment such as verbal, physical, or environmental ([Blackwell et al., 2019](#)). Given that users within IVEs often remain anonymous to other users, how to govern these spaces to ensure the safety of minorities and marginalised groups presents a serious challenge.

In addition to the governance problem, gender and race-related issues have yet to feature in discussions regarding avatar design and virtual body swapping, at least not from an ethical point of view. Yet we know that the way in which intelligent machines are typically portrayed as white “in colour, ethnicity, or both” is illustrative not only of the milieu in which they are typically produced, but also of long-standing ideological structures that relate to race and technology ([Cave & Dihal, 2020](#)). As the use of IVEs becomes more widespread in education, workplace training, and in the provision of public services, it is crucial to ensure that these spaces are accessible, inclusive, and safe for a variety of users.

Finally, in addition to physical and cognitive accessibility (e.g. different bodies and abilities) and content accessibility (e.g. gender and body stereotypes of avatars), another matter of concern revolves around the material access to these kinds of technologies (e.g. infrastructure, money, time, ownership and trends towards subscription-based modes of assetization). For example, researchers have questioned the extent to which IVEs may exacerbate social inequalities and widen the digital divide, based on factors such as income, ethnicity, geography, and education ([Benjamins et al., 2023](#); [Tukur et al., 2023](#); [Kizza, 2003](#); [Franks, 2017](#)). It is clear that access to these technologies may be limited for individuals who lack the necessary technological resources or skills. As [Xu, Zhong, Li, and Yan \(2023\)](#) argue, “addressing the digital divide is crucial for ensuring that the metaverse remains an inclusive and equitable platform for all users, regardless of socioeconomic status, geographical location, or disability” (p. 115).

Public space & digital assets

As suggested earlier, much of the research within VR to date has focused on improving the embodiment, immersion, and presence of the user towards various other ends. Though there has also been some discussion surrounding the preservation of privacy, empathy generation, and concerns regarding accessibility and safety, the extent to which the construction of different spaces within IVEs might shape user experiences deserves further attention. Typically, most talk about architecture in the context of IVEs tends to focus on system architecture, that is, the back-end of these technologies. However, given that existing virtual worlds already demonstrate that these environments can consist of highly imaginative, idealised scenes, or more straightforward representations of everyday reality, we believe that we should also be talking about the architecture of the built environment *within* IVEs as a *new form of public space, that is, virtual spaces that are in principle open and accessible to all, though not necessarily publicly owned*. As [Stephen Carr \(1992\)](#) write, “as public life evolves with the culture, new types of spaces may be needed and old ones discarded or revived” (p. xi). Like them, we take public space to mean “the common ground where people carry out the functional and ritual activities that bind a community, whether in the normal routines of daily life or in periodic festivities” (p. xi). Given that IVEs, much like physical public space, look set to increasingly become “centers of commerce and consumption, as well as places of political surveillance” ([Low & Smith, 2013](#), p. vii), we need to reflect on the connections between virtual public space and political and cultural economy. This is because as [Low and Smith](#) suggest, “public spaces are simultaneously an expression of social power and a force themselves that help shape social relations” (p. vii).

We have already seen how the enormous growth of social media

platforms have changed many of our ideas about public space. Twitter and Facebook (to a lesser extent) have sought to portray their platforms as the public spaces of the digital age. Despite their rhetoric often suggesting otherwise, social media platforms remain private spaces which are privately owned and privately governed. Whether or not IVEs could become the new public spaces of the digital age depends largely upon how they are designed and developed going forwards. It is therefore important to consider the implications of talking about IVEs in this way and what sorts of issues arise when we start thinking about IVEs as a new public space.

People working on the ethics of the built environment have long addressed questions about the design, development, and maintenance of public space. Drawing on such discussions, it seems safe to assume that much like physical public spaces, the ways in which virtual public spaces will come together will be largely driven by the relative diversity (or lack thereof) of their designers (Bonsiepe, 2006) and users (Carmona, 2019). In addition, much like physical public spaces, when we start talking about IVEs as a virtual public space, questions of functionality and purpose emerge. For example, is the space conducive to fulfilling the role that a public space should fill? And who gets to decide about this? Users? Owners of the infrastructure? How should IVEs, as public spaces, be governed? With these questions comes other trickier ones, questions that already apply to the delicate distinction between public and private space in physical reality. For example, what forms of content, or behaviour are permissible and who gets to decide how it is policed? Who has liability for harms incurred while using IVEs, whether physical or emotional? Though these questions may appear largely speculative, they are also crucially questions both of and for design.

While we can (and should) look to existing work on the ethics of built environments for guidance regarding the ethics of virtual environments, there are also a number of concerns that are unique to emerging virtual spaces, such as the potential for new and increased levels of surveillance. In addition, when it comes to IVEs, another set of important questions revolves around the ownership, collecting, and curating of digital entities. From clothing and artwork to property and land, virtual shops and asset libraries provide users with the opportunity to buy and sell various objects, including non-fungible tokens (NFTs). Blockchain technology can be used in order to create decentralised platforms where users can buy and sell objects using these tokens, effectively allowing them to build and shape the virtual environment as they please. While on the one hand this system opens up the design and development of the space for user interaction and engagement, there is the risk that asset-based systems simply perpetuate existing economic inequalities within virtual worlds. This is why how we address these issues going forwards is both a matter for governance as well as design and why ethics by design approaches are so important (Rathenau Instituut, 2020; Radziwill, 2019; Spiegel, 2018).

Etiquette & governance

Having introduced some of the questions that are triggered by the distinction between private and public spaces, another important question that emerges concerns what modes of governance are most appropriate within these kinds of environments (Dwivedi et al., 2022; Fernandez & Hui, 2022; Ning et al., 2023). As we have seen, the ways in which particular norms and values guide the design and development of virtual public spaces requires careful consideration. We therefore also need to think about the creation of norms, regulations, and governance structures within IVEs environments. But how can and should VR spaces be governed? What does governance mean in the context of IVEs? How do we deal with the question of governance when it comes to spaces where the very fabric of perceptual reality (and the underlying infrastructure) within the space is itself by default proprietary? The democratic use of public space relies on the possibility for users to transform the space and repurpose in relation to different values and aims. In other words, a fundamental dimension of the publicness of public space is its

hackability (Sendra et al., 2022). Concerning methods of governance, codes of conduct for users, developers, and curators of these spaces, need to be developed. These will need to be agreed through mechanisms specific to the different environments, depending on user agreement about what forms of private or public governance are appropriate to the IVE space and its use. Attention should also be given to other methods of oversight – particularly towards the question as to whether these environments are going to be considered primarily public or private spaces.

What remains a highly relevant ethical and political concern is control over construction, curation, and control of digital objects and environments in IVEs and how possibilities for agency within an IVE, including transformation of the fundamental rules of (various) forms of engagement, are mediated politically (through governance) as well as technically? At the horizon of these types of concerns, is the question of the governance of proprietary AI agents operating within IVEs and interacting with human users in various ways, including attempting to manipulate behaviour. In other words, how are IVEs and the artificial agents that might populate them governed and by whom? Anderson (2015) offers a distinction between “public” and “private” governance that is highly relevant to the political and technical governance of IVEs.

You are subject to private government wherever (a) you are subordinate to authorities who can order you around and sanction you for not complying over some domain of your life, and (b) the authorities treat it as none of your business, across a wide range of cases, what orders it issues or why it sanctions you. A government is private with respect to a subject if it can issue orders, backed by sanctions, to that subject in some domain of that subject’s life, and that subject has no say in how that government operates and no standing to demand that their interests be taken into account, other than perhaps in narrowly defined circumstances, in the decisions that government makes.

By this definition, private government can extend to spaces that are otherwise considered public, in the sense of being open and in principle accessible to all. As commercial, social and political activity within IVEs becomes more commonplace, the question of private governance of such environments will become increasingly relevant.

In contrast to the notion of a lived environment (or part of an environment) being privately governed, Lefebvre (1968) coined the expression *Le Droit à la Ville* (right to the city) to refer not only to the right to access to civic and public goods (e.g. rights), but also the right of residents to exercise collective power in transforming their lived environments. Similarly to the notion of private government, it is likely that the idea of a “*Droit à la Ville*” in IVEs will become increasingly relevant if and when VR use becomes increasingly prevalent and a more common medium of commercial, social, and political interaction. Questions concerning the democratic governance of IVEs are not limited in their scope to the IVEs themselves. Bibri and Allam (2022) compare the Metaverse concept to a virtual smart city in terms of levels of data-veillance and argue that IVEs (they refer to the Metaverse as a general concept) will serve to further normalise dataveillance, behaviour manipulation and social sorting practices in PR as well in IVEs.

The privateness of IVEs (in terms of ownership and governance) also extends from a political to an ontological level. The experiential environment itself within an IVE is potentially subject to private ownership and levels of control that seemingly extend far beyond PR and with that the possibilities for transformation. This can be thought about in terms of property relations but also the kind of skills and capabilities necessary to engage in transformative activity within an IVE and whether users have readily available access to these. There is a long-standing discussion within political theory and political psychology concerning the importance of privacy (e.g. Westin 2003) and more narrowly anonymity (Bachmann, Knecht, and Wittel (2017) for democratic political agency. For example, from a formal point of view, the idea of ever-increasing social transparency and granularity of information about the lives of subjects extending to physiology and behavioural minutiae as a predictor of social and political behaviour is closely linked to early theoretical articulations of totalitarian government. Bay (2023), drawing on

the political phenomenology of Hannah Arendt, also points to the risk that hyper-personalisation or individualisation of experiences within supposedly public virtual spaces undermines the capacity for democratic governance of those space, as the latter requires an underpinning of common forms of experience in order to ground the deliberation and collective decision making that are required for democratic governance. Thus even if formal mechanisms for democratic governance of IVEs were to be put in place, the efficacy of these mechanisms could be undermined by the hyper-personalised user-experience of the IVE which prevents formations of shared norms and values needed for democratic governance. A related but distinct concern is raised by Munn and Wieijers (2023). They argue that time and efforts invested by users into IVEs will make these virtual spaces morally, socially and politically valuable to users. Users may also have salient aspects of their personal and social identities tied up with the use of virtual spaces. However, due to the private ownership and governance of IVEs, users will be at risk that the spaces face closure or radical transformation in line with the (profit) motives of private owners. Parallel to the closure or making inaccessible of public spaces in PR, this risk to well-being and identity would be borne by users. In any case, the ways in which particular norms and values will guide the design, development, and use of virtual public spaces requires careful, ongoing consideration.

Conclusion

As has been the case in the field of AI, many working within VR have begun to call for a focus on human-centred design, prioritising the human element of VR rather than its technical implementation (Jerald, 2015). Also much like AI, the applications of VR are extensive and range across numerous domains of knowledge (see Slater and Sanchez-Vives 2016 for a review). Architects and urban planners use VR to visualise large industrial developments (Song et al., 2018) while surgeons use VR models to simulate surgical procedures (Alaraj et al., 2011; Gallagher et al., 2005). VR is also being used for therapeutic purposes, such as in the treatment of phobias, anxiety disorders, schizophrenia, depression, and eating disorders (Freeman et al., 2017), as well as in the rehabilitation of violent offenders (Seinfeld et al., 2018). Other possibilities abound, from simulating doctor/patient interactions, to rehabilitating prisoners, from facilitating virtual travel to improving remote collaboration (Slater & Sanchez-Vives, 2016). But as the initial responses to the *We Met...* trailer demonstrate, the proliferation of VR environments is generating numerous complex and nuanced ethical questions that need to be carefully considered if VR is to be used in ways that will be societally beneficial.

In this contribution, we have provided an overview of emerging ethical issues in the context of IVEs. We have also pointed to the relevance of phenomenological approaches in elucidating and methodologically approaching some of these questions. As we pointed out, while some of these concerns are already visible in existing VR spaces, others are far more anticipatory and speculative. Of course, in recent years, ethical AI has been through several waves of development, becoming a key topic of discussion in scientific, business, and government circles. This has helped raise public awareness as to the opportunities and risks of AI. However internationally speaking, there has, as yet, been little public or political discussion of VR generally or IVEs more specifically, despite the wide range of social and ethical issues its use could entail (Rathenau, 2020). Specifically, we have shown that when it comes to IVEs, attention is required to issues such as privacy (e.g. what user data will IVEs require and how will that data be collected and stored), safety (e.g. how to ensure IVEs are safe, inclusive spaces that avoid many of the issues already encountered in VR), social interaction (e.g. how do users behave, engage, and interact with different human and non-human agents), and governance (e.g. how are IVEs built and according to what rules will they operate). For while abstract ethical consideration of these factors may have become commonplace in discussions concerning both AI and VR, their convergence in the context of IVEs warrants

nuanced and ongoing reflection, ideally building upon the actual accounts and experiences of users.

In this sense, we need to ask critical questions about how we want IVEs to function, look, and feel in the future. We recognise that, as Phil Agre writes, the relationship between technical practice, and attempts to guide that technical practice are complex (Agre, 1997). We also agree with Richard Sennet when he says, “the jaggedness between lived and built cannot be resolved simply by the planner displaying ethical uprightness” (Sennett, 2018, p. 3). Yet as we have shown, IVEs present a variety of complex socio-political, economic, and philosophical questions. Dealing with the jaggedness of IVEs will therefore require more than producing ethical guidelines and codes of conduct. We hope this piece serves as a prompt to open up discussion surrounding the ethics of IVEs and encourage those in the field to consider the various ways and means of doing ethics by design.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Danielle Shanley: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Darian Meacham:** Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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